

Extremization of Pressure in Statistical Mechanics and Extreme Physical Information

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The notion of extremizing Shannon's entropy subject to constraints is well known in classical statistical mechanics (e.g. in the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas). There, however, the maximization of the number of arrangements is the key physical idea. Alternatively, in dynamics there exists the extremization of Extreme Physical Information (EPI) (which makes use of Fisher's information) (1). This may be used to derive Newton's equations (from the Lagrangia) and the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

We suggest there exists a unifying idea, namely the extremization of pressure subject to constraints, which accounts for both the extremization of entropy and (EPI). We argue that this is the key idea behind the two seemingly different extremization approaches.

The Concept of Pressure in a Classical Gas

Pressure in a classical Maxwell-Boltzmann (ideal) gas is a key physical idea, yet it is not used explicitly in either the maximization of entropy subject to constraints or reaction balance. It usually appears as a consequence of the equilibrium distribution. A hint of its importance follows from the fact that one may use $PV=nRT$ (P =pressure, T =temperature, V =volume etc) together with a pressure force balance on a tiny box i.e.

$$P(x+dx) - P(x) = \text{density}(x) \text{ Force}(x) \quad \text{where } \text{density}(x)=n/V \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } \text{density}(x) = C \exp(-V(x)/T) \quad ((2))$$

The approach ((1)), however, does not explicitly involve extremization. Implicitly, however, it does because it follows from Newton's second law which in turn follows from an extremization of Fisher's information subject to a constraint (i.e. EPI) as will be later shown. It may be noted, however, that $PV=nRT$ is also used and this does not follow from EPI, so there are two different equilibrium issues to deal with. It would be good to unify the two , we argue.

Pressure in a Free Quantum Particle

A free quantum particle is represented by the wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. One might argue that one only has momentum present, i.e. p , but momentum is physically equivalent to an impulse which may be delivered at any instant (i.e. if the particle strikes a target). We have argued in previous notes that a quantum free particle manifests the physical impulse even when it is not striking a target through the two x -probability distributions $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$, The bigger the impulse, the sharper the slope, i.e. $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ (just like $-dV/dx$). The free particle, however, has a second attached piece of behaviour (information), namely its average speed given by p/m (nonrelativistically). Thus it is not simply the case that the particle may deliver an impulse of p , but this impulse is delivered in a time proportional to the speed p/m . This leads to the classical idea of pressure:

Pressure is proportional to impulse * speed ((3))

Pressure in a Bound Quantum System

If a free particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)$, one may suggest an ensemble for a bound single particle in a potential $V(x)$ i.e.:

$$W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$$

This leads to the notion of an average impulse:

$$\text{Average impulse} = -i\hbar \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((4a))$$

This may be used in a classical expression for pressure by multiplying by physical density $W(x)W(x)$ and average speed proportional to ((4a)) divided by m . One may note that in a quantum system one does not follow the particle through $x(t)$, so one cannot form the usual classical statistical quantity $\text{Average}(pv)$. Rather, one multiplies an average impulse by an average speed to obtain:

$$\text{Average pressure in a bound state} = W(x)W(x) \{-i\hbar \frac{dW}{dx} / W\} \{-i\hbar \frac{dW}{dx} / W\} \quad ((5))$$

((5)), however, is exactly the expression for the statistical quantity called Fisher's information.

As a result, we argue that the notion of pressure is key in both a classical Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, with or without a potential $V(x)$, a quantum free particle and a single quantum bound state. In other words, we try to argue that pressure is a unifying concept. We next consider the usual extremization procedures used in statistical mechanics and dynamics.

The Extremization/Variation of the Lagrangian

It is well known that Newton's second law follows from the extremization of a Lagrangian which is usually given by kinetic energy - $V(x)$. This leads to $d/dt \ dL/dx = -dV/dx$. We note that the classical kinetic energy $.5mv^2$ is proportional to the classical idea of pressure which is constant $*p*v$. The extremization of the Lagrangian is said to follow from the extremization of Fisher's information subject to the constraint $V(x)$ i.e. EPI (1). In such a case, Fisher's information is written as:

$$I = \text{Fisher's information} = \int dt \ \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} \quad ((6))$$

Thus it is argued that Newtonian mechanics follow from the extremization of a dynamic quantity which is proportional to the notion of pressure.

The Maximization of Entropy

A traditional approach in classical statistical mechanics is to maximize a quantity called Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i f(i) \ln(f(i))$ (where $f(i)$ is the probability for i) subject to constraints. Physically, this approach is said to maximize the number of arrangements in a system. In particular, maximizing:

$$- \sum_i f(i) \ln(f(i)) + b E \rightarrow f(i) = C \exp(-eb) \text{ where } b=1/\text{Temperature} \quad ((7))$$

It should be noted that in a classical gas, particles move according to Newton's law when they are not colliding. Newton's law, however, follows from EPI extremization as argued in the above section. Why is a second, different extremization needed? It seems that Newton's second law does not give the proportions $f(e_i)$ where $e_i = pp/2m$ of a particle which undergoes elastic collisions. A different principle is needed for this, but the final consequence is that it yields the pressure in the system. For a single particle, pressure is proportional to $p v$, but one needs to know how many particles have $e = pp/2m$ i.e. $f(e)$. Given a total energy in the system of E and N particles, this becomes a distribution problem. If there are no rules weighting the distributions, one may consider all possible arrangements of E partitioned over N particles, each with a weight of 1. This is exactly the argument of traditional statistical mechanics. From these, one may calculate average $f(e)$ values. The usual calculational approach, however, is to write the \ln number of possible arrangements:

$$\ln \{ N! / \text{Product of } i \ n(e_i)! \} \quad ((8))$$

and maximize ((8)) subject to an average energy constraint $E = \sum_i e_i f(e_i)$. Thus the entire focus is on maximizing the possible ways to distribute energy to N particles. The result, however, leads to an average pressure so one may argue that pressure is extremized in a certain manner.

Interestingly, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution also follows from reaction balance which does not maximize any quantity explicitly. One considers an elastic collision of two particles and argues that the product probabilities before the collision equals that after i.e.

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((9a)) \text{ and } f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((9b))$$

This holds for any $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$, thus there is a kind of loss of information. One may argue that ((9a)) is proportional to a kind of pressure of single particles before and after the collision. The energy in the system is then distributed so that:

$$\ln(f(e_i)) \text{ is proportional to the average pressure of single particle with } e_i = pp/2m \quad ((10))$$

Thus reaction balance also points to an approach based on pressure, in fact the information ($\ln(f(e))$) is proportional to the single particle pressure. Then $f(e) \ln(f(e))$ is the average pressure contributed by a particular e .

Quantum Free Particle

A quantum free particle is represented by a square root probability of $\exp(ipx)$, but maps to $P(x) = \exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx) = 1$. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ follow from the extremization of Fisher's information subject to $\int \cos(px)\cos(px) = \text{constant}$ (and a similar expression for $\sin(px)$). One extremizes:

$$d/dx \cos(px) \quad d/dx \cos(px) + b \cos(px)\cos(px) \quad (\text{with an identical expression for } \sin(px)) \quad ((11))$$

This yields: $d/dx \quad d/dx \cos(px) = -b \cos(px) \quad ((12))$

We argue that p represents an impulse and $d/dx \cos(px) \quad d/dx \cos(px)$ a component of internal pressure.

Quantum Bound State

In the above section, we argued that a quantum free particle contains two spatial distributions $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ linked to internal pressure. What happens for a quantum single particle bound state? We argue that instead of $\exp(ipx)$, one uses an ensemble:

$$W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((13))$$

This leads to a superposition of internal pressures to yield an overall average:

$$\text{Average pressure} = \int W(x)W(x) \{-idW/dx / W\} \{-idW/dx / W\} \quad ((14))$$

For a classical system, one creates the average: $p v = f(pp/2m)$. In the quantum case there is no time within a wavelength i.e. there is a probability distribution in x , so it is not really correct to write $p v = \exp(ipx)$. As a result, one creates an average impulse term: $-idW/dx / W$ and then considers this to also be proportional to an average "velocity" linked to impulse. Thus one arrives at ((14)). Why doesn't one extremize entropy? We argue that for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas $\ln(f(e))$ is proportional to pressure for a single particle with e so $N \ln(f(e))$ is the pressure contributed from all particles with this e . For the quantum case, the pressure is given by ((14)) which contains Fisher's information. Thus one consistently extremizes average pressure, but pressure may be expressed in different ways in different systems. ((14)) is extremized subject to $\int W(x)W(x) = 1$. This then yields the Schrodinger equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although two seemingly different extremization approaches exist, namely maximization of entropy and extremization of Fisher's information subject to constraints (EPI), they are both linked to extremization of pressure. Thus we argue that there is a unifying physical principle at work. In a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, single particle pressure is proportional

to $\ln(f(e_i))$ (information) because for reaction balance: $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$. Thus $f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ (-entropy) is really proportional to average pressure which is extremized subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E$.

We argue that a free quantum particle $\exp(ipx)$ contains internal pressure and that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represent pieces of this pressure represented by: $\cos(px)\cos(px) \{ d/dx \ln(\cos(px) \cos(px)) \}$ subject to the constraint $\int \cos(px)\cos(px) = \text{constant}$ (and a similar expression for $\sin(px)$). This may then be extremized to yield: $d/dx d/dx \cos(px) = b \cos(px)$ i.e. the Schrodinger equation with no $V(x)$. In the case of a $V(x)$, $\exp(ipx) \rightarrow W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In this case, $f(e) \ln(f(e))$ no longer describes pressure. One might suggest $\{ \sum_p a(p) p v \exp(ipx) \} / W(x)$, but v is not defined within a wavelength because one has a probability scheme. Thus we propose an average impulse multiplied by itself divided by m multiplied by $W(x)W(x)$. This is exactly Fisher's information which may be extremized subject to the constraint $\int W(x)W(x)=1$, yielding the Schrodinger equation (time independent version).

Thus we argue that the extremization of pressure subject to constraints is a unifying principle behind the two extremization procedures, entropy and Fisher's information (EPI).

References

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